

BP-MoGeRe - Data Repository

This Zenodo repository is reserved for the BP-MoGeRe feasibility study.

Study title:

Blended physiotherapy in mobile geriatric rehabilitation: a feasibility study

Principal Investigator:

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Institution:

Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg, Department of Physiotherapy

Study registration:

Registration in the German Clinical Trials Register (DRKS) pending, currently in preparation.

Ethics approval:

Ethics application submitted to the Ethics Committee of Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg. Ethics approval pending.

Study protocol:

The study protocol is planned for publication and will subsequently be uploaded to Zenodo (expected: 2026).

Data availability:

Anonymized study data will be uploaded to this repository upon study completion (expected: 2028).

For questions, please contact:

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